

Fresh eyes on CMIP

Idea initially came out of Data Request subgroup, from Chloe Mackallah and Martin Jukes (DR TT Co-leads). Developed into CMIP-wide initiative by IPO.

Researchers, scientists and practitioners early in their career provide a unique insight into climate science. Coming into the system more recently enables ECRs* to have a fresh perspective on CMIP. ECRs regularly undertake the, often time consuming, task of generating, downloading, processing, and analysing data from CMIP and as such, have a unique, working insight into the successes and flaws of CMIP phases. Fresh eyes on CMIP would be a new working group comprised of scientists, researchers, and practitioners in the early stages of their careers to sit alongside the CMIP7 task teams. See final page of PDF for more information on generic Fresh Eyes review infosheet. Fresh eyes on CMIP will also work to significantly increase collaborations with scientists working in the global south.

*ECR definition

Early career researchers (ECRs) are master and PhD students, researchers, and practitioners in the early stages of their career. Typical definitions of ECRs suggest this period is within seven years of obtaining their highest degree (excluding career breaks). We will not impose this strict time definition but include it for reference. Application is open to all scientists, researchers and practitioners in the early stages of their career. Practitioners are those working at the interface of society, policy, practice, and research.

Objectives and Goals

1. Directly integrate the voice of ECRs into CMIP.
2. Provide invaluable insight into the generation and access of CMIP data.
3. Creating opportunities and encouraging participation for ECRs in the CMIP community
4. Engage ECRs in the broader scientific and research community intersecting academia, NGOs, private sector, and Governmental institutions.
5. Present proposals to the CMIP Panel and CMIP7 Task Teams
6. Opportunity for task team liaisons to attend task team meetings.
7. Opportunity for co-leads to attend (wider) panel meetings
8. Work with IPO on CMIP carbon accounting and identify avenues for reducing the carbon footprint of CMIP.
9. Work with IPO on designing dedicated CMIP ECR activities and increasing ECR involvement in wider activities.

Group size

Size of the group can be flexible. There will be two co-leads, in line with other task teams. Each existing CMIP7 task team would have one or two liaisons in the Fresh Eyes on CMIP group. The co-leads acting as liaisons for the Panel. Therefore, group size should lie between nine to sixteen members.

Time commitment

Meetings are expected to take place regularly, every 2-3 months, and more frequently as required and at the discretion of the co-leads. There may be times when there is more or less work depending on the activities undertaken (e.g., a peak period may be associated with a workshop or paper published by the group). Due to the international nature of the group. Most meetings will be online, with some out-of-hours working required to the challenges of time zone coordination.

Remuneration

As with all CMIP7 task teams and committees, these will not be paid roles.

Calls for membership

There will be three membership calls held across 2023 (and early 2024). We will launch an initial application call at the ECR EGU townhall in April 2023. Additional calls will be launched at the Open Science Conference in Rwanda (October 2023) and at AGU (December 2023). Calls will be shared as widely as possible, using these conferences as initial platforms. This group aims to significantly increase the engagement of young global south scientists within CMIP. As such, scientists in the global south are particularly encouraged to apply. We will also utilise the YESS network, Twitter, LinkedIn, and newsletters/networks from EGU, AGU, JpGU, AOGS. Additional advertising avenues will be researched.

Fresh Eyes

What is it?

Fresh Eyes is looking afresh at what is going on or a situation and is most effective when people from outside the team are brought in.

It can be used as part *of Creative Problem Solving (CPS)* specifically to help generate fresh perspectives.

In this context, Fresh Eyes is often used in conjunction with the *Go See* tool to deeply understand what is really happening.

Why use it?

It can be really revelatory to bring in people from outside the team, whether those with specific expertise in the Focus methodology or those who are unfamiliar with the area or process, as they can help to generate fresh perspectives without the biases that can come from being overfamiliar with the process.

Use the 'fresh eyes' of new members of staff. Specifically ask them for their thoughts, from their own experiences working in other organisations, of what they have learnt that could help you improve the processes here.

Use the 'collective intelligence' of the team to bring all your ideas and concepts together and generate new ideas to find solutions in an 'ideal world'.

Benefits at a glance ...

- generates new ideas by providing a view of a situation from very different perspectives
- it's most effective when employed after you have already done a fair amount of work and could benefit from a new perspective from those unfamiliar with the process
- uses the 'fresh eyes' of new members of staff to gain differing perspectives